

Principal registered archaeological finds from the surface in South-Limburg (NL) and adjacent areas.

FLINT & NATURAL STONE

Part 1: Flint Axes and Picks

BHG3

ST

VRBC 234

PLCBB

LSM 0141

VRBC

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 FLINT & NATURAL STONE Part 1: Flint Axes and Picks
 L. Jimmy Groen, Gulpen-Wittem

Methods of reporting

Any field survey must end with registering and documentation of objects. This is part 1 of on-line publication of surface finds from the period 2003 – 2017. This first part of a series called “Principal registered archaeological finds from the surface in South-Limburg (NL) and adjacent areas” is about flint axes and mining picks. The word ‘principal’ is referring to a selection made on most important finds made during field surveys. The adjacent areas are located just across the border with Belgium and Germany. This report only contains minimum information on found objects. The Id- numbers start again in each part of the series. Coordinates, if available, have been taken from Google Maps. In the field, if coordinates were taken, this was with help of a GPS App by *MobiWIA – EclipSim* (accuracy based on satellites). The accuracy is between 5-10 m from given coordinates. If coordinates are absent, the find location is not otherwise specified than by a general coordinate in (the center of) the field indicated by GC (General Coordinates) behind the coordinates. The *location* (community/field) name in coordinates is according to Google Maps (2018). For the dimensions, the maximum sizes are measured. Weight is measured in whole grams.

The context of discovery is a very brief description of relative find circumstances; a short description of the object is given by main important characteristics, visible with the naked eye. Images have been made with a simple pocket camera Sony 20.1 where every object has been photographed from its dorsal- and ventral view/ side- and front view and has been adapted with help of *Paint.net*. References from existing literature are added in the end of this paper.

Flint axes and mining picks

During the entire prehistory South -Limburg has been an interesting place for the presence of flint, used by both Paleolithic / Mesolithic hunter - gatherers and Neolithic and Bronze Age settlers. Flint axe heads were very common finds in the fields of South Limburg, so were picks in the mining areas. The flint axes in this report are not of the ‘nice quality and appearance’ like many polished, shiny and cool looking axes we might find on the internet or in exhibitions. Conversely, the examples shown here are either unfinished objects giving some insight on the setup of a flint axe head, or are discarded, broken objects in the final stage of the *chaîne opératoire* of a flint axe head. Two examples of ‘flakes’ with polishing traces, presented in this report are parts of former polished axe heads, which often were re-used as scrapers. In some axe fragments, even cavities have been applied, when necessary for a renewed, completely different use. Most objects shown in this reports are setups or half products of axes, several others are (severely) damaged polished axes and this all is showing something of real Neolithic life: axes presented here are absolutely not museum -quality objects, but daily life items that often were intensively used before finally discarded and left in the field. Mining picks have been used for the mining of flint to break the more soft calcareous horizons around the flint cores to get it out of the layers. These mining picks are without exception made from local flint. Three different types are described by P.J.Sj. Felder (Rademakers, 1998); in this report this distinction is absent.

Entries *format*

Id-Number with possible former codes, provenance or coordinates (general coordinates: GC)

Dimensions (LxWxH in cm, maximum), weight (in rounded grams)

Context of discovery (field, forest, soil type, etc.)

Description

Context date

Image(s) *format*: dorsal/ ventral view; lateral view/ transverse or front view

1.1. Flint Axes

001 field VRBC Rijckholt Sint Geertruid 50.798766, 5.748730

9.5 x 4.0 x 1.8 60g

Field north and adjacent to flint mines of Rijckholt

Black – grey *Rijckholt* flint type. Large part of polishing still visible. Secondarily adapted Neolithic flint axe head, retouches for re-use. Thin blade, oval shape, symmetric cutting edge, asymmetric horizontal axis.

3500-2100 BC

002 field EMW Eckelraderweg Sint Geertruid 50.808311, 5.795141

9.5 x 3.7 x 1.8 65g

Field North of Eckelraderweg. Partially eroded loess horizon with gravels, field near possible former spring and open air flint mining (crossing with Valkenburgerweg, from rounded pits).

Axe head with pointed tip with oval cross-section. Black – grey *Rijckholt* flint type. Very small part of polishing visible at tip. Secondarily adapted Neolithic flint axe head, retouches for re-use.

Asymmetric horizontal axis, asymmetric cutting edge.

3500-2100 BC

003 BHGN Banholt 50.794172, 5.791785 GC

8.5 x 4.0 x 1.8 65g

Field northwest of Banholt flint mines north west of *Herkenradergrubbe*. Possible small Neolithic site.

A thin-leaved axe head with rectangular cross-section and wide cutting edge. Light grey flint type with large white dots. Iron stains by plowing. Some traces of polishing. Secondarily adapted with large retouches on edges. Symmetric cutting edge.

3500-2100 BC

004 VRBC Rijckholt. Sint Geertruid 50.799156, 5.748000 GC

8.5 x 4.0 x 1.8 64g

Field north of Schoone Grub , Neolithic flint mines

Local *Rijckholt* flint, secondarily adapted Neolithic flint axe head with small traces of polishing.

3500-2100 BC

005 ST Schneeberg Aachen Germany 50.784867, 6.020988 GC

8.5 x 4.8 x 1.8 82 g

Top of Schneeberg in loess cover, found at same field as Roman watch tower was located
Lousberg flint type, with fine retouches at one side, no traces of polishing; *Tranchet* – type, the principal cutting edge is heavily retouched

3500- 2100 BC

006 VRBC 234 Sint Geertruid 50.799156, 5.748000 GC

10.8 x 5.0 (1.6) x 2.1 125 g

Field north of Schoone Grub, adjacent to Neolithic flint mines

Setup of a flint axe head, one side unfinished. Grey *Rijckholt* flint, broken tip, no traces of polishing, typical Rijckholt patinas. The large wide side has a hollow concave, unifacial retouched part

3500-2100 BC

007 SMV 64 (410) St. Martensvoeren Kattenroth 3798 Voeren, Belgium 50.755470, 5.812920 GC

10.1 x 5.5 x 2.6 164g

Field north of St. Martensvoeren/ Fourn St. Martin. Context is loess loam with some gravels and some marl stone

Grey flint with polishing traces on ventral side, one pointed side (pick model)

3500-2100 BC

008 SGK Sint Geertruid 50.788970, 5.741606 GC

8.1 x 4.5 x 1.6 60 g

Location named "De Kaap" at St. Geertruid, field with loess

Fragment of a polished pick shape (chisel) originally with complete rounded sides in light grey flint with tiny black inclusions ; discarded

3500 -2100 BC

remark:007=wrong indicated

009 BHG3 Banholt. Mheer 50.789217, 5.798222

8.1 x 4.5 x 1.6 70 g

South of open air flint mines of Banholt

Flint axe head in grey flint type with tiny black inclusions (similar to nr 008) no polishing, raw adapted shape. Some white patina stains. Symmetric horizontal axis.

3500 -2100 BC

010 VRBD Margraten 50.799346, 5.749416 GC

12.8 x 6.2 x 3.2 230g

Field is adjacent to VRBC and north of Schoone Grub, part of Neolithic flint mine area of Rijckholt.

Setup of axe head in *Ryckholt* flint, discarded. Some polishing visible at surface. Raisin stains on surface. One side with bluish patinas. Secondarily use of pick (?)

3500 -2100 BC

011 LAN5 115 Bassenge 4690, Belgium 50.781550, 5.669337

14.1 x 9.5 (6.4) x 6.5 675 g

Slightly sloping field over the Jeker/ Geer valley, loess cover; Neolithic flint working site; many flakes were found here as well

Heavy axe head made in local *Hesbaye* flint of Mt. St. Pierre (B). Iron stains due to plowing. Very large butt, probably late Neolithic period

3500 -2100 BC

012 GRD Eys 50.827185, 5.950525

6.8 x 4.5 x 1.7 67g

From a field north of the Castle "Goedenraad" near Eijs (community of Gulpen-Wittem).

Small axe head in grey flint polished and damaged. The cutting edge has been unifacial slightly retouched. The platform is still visible and has been polished as well. Flake removals at both dorsal and ventral side. Straight symmetric horizontal axis and symmetric cutting edge.

3500 -2100 BC

013 LTV Visé Belgium 50.791292, 5.684064

12.5 x 7.5(5.2) x 3.2 304 g

The find location is a field on the plateau edge of Mt. St. Pierre, locally known as "Thier de Vigne".
Broken Neolithic axe head in grey- black flint. With transversal break.

3500 -2100 BC

014 MSP Montagne St. Pierre (B) LAN 77 Bassenge 4690, Belgium 50.783696, 5.673807

12.9 x 8.2 x 4.3 577g

Location LAN 77 is light to the west sloping field, east of the Jeker/ Geer brook at Mt. St. Pierre.
Heavy axe head in light grey *Hesbaye* flint, dorsal side partially covered with patina. Large step fractions in flaking, one longitude edge shows damage, which might be the reason for discarding the object, ventral part hardly adapted; pointed side and symmetric horizontal axis is reason to classify it as axe

3500 -2100 BC

015 VRB-1 Sint Geertruid 50.798255, 5.750446

11.2 x 7.4 x 3.1 444g

This object has been found in a tree- fall, north of the Schoone Grub.

Setup of Neolithic flint axe head in black *Rijckholt* flint. Multi flaking at one side, the other side is adapted by more large blows. The axe is unfinished. Partially there is cortex visible. Well performed symmetric cutting edge

3500 -2100 BC

016 RU Rullen (Bas) Voeren Belgium 50.719442, 5.821839 GC

10.0 x 5.8 x 3.1 203g

Disturbed mining and production site at Rullen- Bas; disturbed by construction of a gas pipeline. Flint axe head setup in locally mined *Rullen* flint. First stage of process in manufacturing the axe head. The ventral side is hardly processed.

3500 -2100 BC

017 PLCB 016 Visé Belgium 50.800158, 5.687547
7.5 x 4.5 x 2.6 111g

Found at the field PLCB at Visé / Riemst Caestert/ Caster. The context is a slightly sloping part of the field where gravels dominate.

Unknown –non local flint type (probably *Rullen?*) where at both sides polishing of the surface is visible; probably this is remains of larger axe. One side has a pointed tip which is asymmetric in shape and the base side contains a deliberately made concave part, secondary used as hammer stone (visible hammering marks) and no cutting edges are present. Wide oval cross section. This could have been a (nice) toy for children.

3500 -2100 BC

018 VVB- 001 Unnamed Road Vaals 50.761684, 5.979120 ±10 - 20 m
10.2 x 5.4 x 3.2 199g

From a forest path in *Vijlenerbos* (forest), without real context. We might wonder if it has been brought up from elsewhere, though the flint type is common for the region.

Grey flint, no polishing

3500 -2100 BC

remark:wrong number indication

019 BHG Mheer 50.788909, 5.797879 GC

13.5 x 6.5 x 4.0 387g

Setup of an axe head from local *Banholt* flint, some brown parts visible, cortex partially present at dorsal side. The sharp cutting edge at one side is well retouched. The oblique broken part would be the reason for discarding the object.

3500 -2100 BC

020 PLC-AC Rue de Caster 4600 Visé, Belgium 50.801899, 5.686811

12.7 x 6.2 x 3.1 362g

Found in the western part of field PLC, labeled PLC -AC; loess context

Traces of polishing are still visible at both sides. All sides are rounded, without cutting edge.

3500 -2100 BC

021 EM 004 (E) Ezelsweg Eijsden 50.773489, 5.734477

10.5 x 5.7 x 3.5 278 g

From a field north of a path called "Ezelsweg"

Axe, originally polished, traces at both sides visible; heavy use and secondary use as hammer-stone, bluish and brown parts in flint, probably *Rullen* type flint

3500 -2100 BC

022 PLCB 014 Visé Belgium 50.800356, 5.686363

8.0 x 4.4 x 2.8 133g

From the PLCB prehistoric site at Visé Caster / Riemst Caestert

Axe head made from *Rullen* type flint, polished, traces of polishing at both sides visible, used and discarded, heavy damage at one side. Oval cross section with more straight sides.

3500 -2100 BC

023 SB2 SEF Aachen Germany 50.786745, 6.044783 ± 10-20 m
10.5 x 5.7 x 2.8 195g

From the location of the expansion of the RWTH Aachen;
Setup of axe head in *Lousberg* flint. Symmetric horizontal axis.
3500 -2100 BC

024 PLCB V4 Visé Belgium 50.800376, 5.687017
9.5 x 6.1 x 3.0 200g

From the PLCB prehistoric site at Visé -Caster / Riemst -Caestert. The field has been used for
manufacture of axes and flint tools demonstrated by finds of many flint cores.
Light grey local *Hesbaye* flint type. Setup of an axe.
3500 -2100 BC

025 LSPX 0141 Visé Belgium 50.776792, 5.675379

9.5 x 6.0 x 2.7 162g

Found at the wall of a grub next to one of the local flint sources/ atelier nearby at the steep side of the Meuse river (dominating the present Albert Canal).

Reshaped axe head from grey flint, local *Heyoule* flint; Dorsal side with some polishing, a pointed shape with concave base; broken tip. Ventral side with partially some cortex, shaping around it in all directions. Unfinished tip.

3500 -2100 BC

026 PLC 406 Visé – Caster Belgium 50.801420, 5.684306

9.3 x 4.6 x 4.2 257g

From the PLCB prehistoric site at Visé Caster / Riemst Caestert

One of the primary stages of setup of an axe head, raw shaped in local *Hesbaye* flint; probably abandoned because of bad quality parts of the flint around the cortex. Oval cross section.

Asymmetric horizontal axis.

3500 -2100 BC

A027 (PLCB -)BB Visé Caster Belgium 50.801420, 5.684306 GC

6.2 x 3.2 x 1.1 24 g

From the utmost southern part of the Visé -Caster prehistoric site.

Small, re- adapted part of former polished axe. Traces of polishing at one side. Rullen type flint.
3500 -2100 BC

A028 SMV Kattenroth 3798 Voeren, Belgium 50.755606, 5.813349 GC

5.1 x 3.8 x 1.2 28g

From a field north of St. Martensvoeren, context is gravels and calcareous fragments in loess

Traces of polishing, *Rullen* flint type.

3500 -2100 BC

029 VRA Sint Geertruid 50.797433, 5.751219

15.7 x 6.9 x 3.1 400g

Object has been found north of Schoone Grub, Rijckholt flint mines.

Raw setup of an axe in light *Rijckholt* flint, broken
3500- 2100 BC

030 RU Rullen (Bas) Voeren Belgium 50.719442, 5.821839 GC

14.2 x 7.2 x 3.4 420 g

From the Rullen – Bas site. Object found in disturbed context because of the gas pipeline construction in the area.

The object is in grey local *Rullen* flint with honey color shine. This setup of an axe still has visible patina at one side.

3500 -2100 BC

1.2. Picks

031 SG Eijsderweg Sint Geertruid 50.791873, 5.755725 GC

8.5 x 6.2 x 2.7 123g

From a field near the Eijsderweg in St. Geertruid

Fragment of a pick. Some shiny patina, a thick cortex is present on this broken part that is well adapted

3500 – 2100 BC

032 MSP no coordinates available

9.5 x 3.4 x 4.0 230g

From the Belgian part of Mt. St. Pierre, south of Maastricht (NL). Its exact location is unknown.

A pointed fragment in grey *Hesbaye* flint. The fragment shows a horizontal axis which is symmetric, which is unusual compared to other picks found in the area.

3500- 2100 BC

033PLCB 122 Visé Belgium 50.800773, 5.686556 GC

11.1 x 4.4 x 2.7 120g

From the southern part of the Visé - Caster prehistoric site

Mining pick made of local flint. Broken tip. Asymmetric horizontal axis (curved), dorsal side is flaked, the bulb of percussion is still visible

3500 -2100 BC

034 EBE 7 Bassenge 4690, Belgium 50.778331, 5.663436

11.2 x 5.5 x 3.9 237g

From a field from a location known as Lava; the field shows intense erosion and a paleosol was visible.

Pick in *Hesbaye* flint with visible patinas, the cortex is partially present. The object has a weathered appearance compared to other finds from this region. The ventral side is not processed

3500- 2100 BC

035 SGK-01 Sint Geertruid 50.788129, 5.740833 GC

13.2 x 4.6 x 2.8 190g

From a location named "De Kaap".

Grey *Rijckholt* flint with patinas. The ventral side has a broken part which shows the original flint type.

3500- 2100 BC

036 VRB –C Sint Geertruid 50.798248, 5.749116

10.5 x 6.4 x 2.8 144g

From the Rijckholt flint mines area, northern part adjacent to "Schoone Grub"; found in a colluvial horizon of a field.

Grey pick made from *Rijckholt* flint. The ventral side is broken.

3500 -2100 BC

037VR08 Sint Geertruid 50.799902, 5.756240

9.8 x 3.5 x 1.4 60 g

From a field from the north side and adjacent to the Schoone Grub. This field was part of the mining area of Rijckholt.

Pick made on a large flake in *Rijckholt* flint
3500 -2100 BC

Mining pick, hafted on antler bone

References

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Rademakers, P.C.M. (eindred.) (1998) De prehistorische vuursteenmijnen van Ryckholt-St. Geertruid, Afdeling Limburg der Nederlandse Geologische Vereniging, Beek pp. 193-197

Outline of this series

(Expected from 2018 without end date)

Note: date of publication is not consecutively by number in this list and is depending on depot, so the order of publications may vary. All parts will show a *selection* of important finds.

FLINT & NATURAL STONE

Part 1: Flint axes and picks

Part 2a: Flint cores

Part 2b: Hammerstones

Part 3: Polishing stones/ various natural stones

Part 4a: Neolithic flint tools on blades

Part 4b: Neolithic flint tools on flakes

Part 5: Various Neolithic objects

Part 6: Mesolithic flint objects

Part 7: Middle Paleolithic flint objects

Part 8: Non - flint stone tools

POTTERY SHARDS

Part 1: Selection of Prehistoric pottery

Part 2: Selection of Roman pottery

Part 3: Selection of Stoneware pottery

Part 4: Selection of Medieval – sub recent pottery

Part 5: Selection of Building ceramics

METAL FINDS (not detector finds)

Part 1: Coins

Part 2: Various metal objects

BONE/ ORGANIC

Part 1: Bones

Part 2: Loam, charcoal

GLASS

Part 1: Selection of glass and opaque glass finds (beads, etc)

MISCELENEOUS

Part 1: various uncategorized objects

All objects in this series are for educational purpose.